

**IDENTIFIKASI KEANEKARAGAMAN JENIS ROTAN
(*Calamus Sp.*) DI KAWASAN HUTAN ADAT LEMBAH
SENENGGAN DESA DURIAN KAWAN KECAMATAN
KLUET TIMUR-ACEH SELATAN**

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ABSTRAK

*The Senenggan Valley Traditional Forest Area, Durian Kawan Village, East Kluet District, is located in South Aceh Regency, which is located in Aceh Province. The Leuser Ecosystem Area (KEL) is a buffer zone of the Gunung Leuser National Park (TNGL), which has a good collection of rattan with a wide variety of rattan. However, the type and amount of rattan scattered in the area is not yet known. The purpose of this study 1) To determine the types of rattan in the Senenggan Valley Traditional Forest, Durian Kawan Village, East Kluet District, South Aceh. 2) To determine the diversity of rattan plants based on altitude in the area of the Senenggan Valley Traditional Forest, Durian Kawan Village, East Kluet District, South Aceh. This study used a qualitative method. The results of this study indicate 1) There are 6 types of rattan in the Senenggan Valley Indigenous Forest area, namely Jernang rattan (*Daemonorops didymophylla* Becc.), Wax rattan (*Calamus javensis* Blume.), Manan rattan (*Calamus manan* Miq.), Taman rattan (*Calamus caesius* Blume.) Sega Ayer rattan (*Calamus caesius* Blume.) and Dahan rattan (*Korthalsia rigida* Blume.). 2) The diversity (H') of rattan species in the Senenggan Valley Indigenous Forest Area is categorized as low with a Diversity index (H') of 0.73. 3) The most common type of rattan is branched rattan (*Korthalsia rigida* Blume.) with a total of 13 rattan sticks.*

Keywords: Species Diversity, rattan.